

Boosting Data Monetisation with DATAMITE

Jordi Arjona Aroca¹[0000-0002-1761-5170], María José López Osa²[0000-0002-7633-095X], Urtza Iturraspe Barturen²[0000-0003-2740-4294], Vasileios Siopidis³[0000-0001-7677-7957], Konstantinos Votis³[0000-0001-6381-8326], Anastasios Nikolakopoulos⁴[0000-0002-8054-5670], Eftymios Chondrogiannis⁴[0000-0003-3865-2277], Marcin Plociennik⁵[0000-0002-2355-2161], Joel Himanen⁶[0009-0007-8201-9336], Achilleas Marinakis⁷[0000-0001-6785-2361], and Konstantinos Nestorakis⁷[0000-0001-9964-6490]

¹ Instituto Tecnológico de Informática (ITI), Valencia, Spain jarjona@iti.es;

² Tecnalía, Basque Research & Technology Alliance (BRTA), Bilbao, Spain
[{mariajose.lopez, urtza.iturraspe}@tecnalia.com](mailto:mariajose.lopez,urtza.iturraspe@tecnalia.com);

³ CERTH, Center for Research Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece [{vasisiop, kvotis}@iti.gr](mailto:{vasisiop,kvotis}@iti.gr)

⁴ Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, National Technical University of Athens, Greece [{tasosnikolakop, chondrog}@mail.ntua.gr](mailto:{tasosnikolakop,chondrog}@mail.ntua.gr);

⁵ PSNC, Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry PAS, Poznan, Poland
marcinp@man.poznan.pl

⁶ 1001Lakes, Helsinki, Finland joel.himanen@1001lakes.com

⁷ OTE Group of Companies, Athens, Greece [{amarinaki, knestorak}@ote.gr](mailto:{amarinaki,knestorak}@ote.gr);

Abstract. Companies around the globe store large quantities of data they cannot monetise. Regarding internal monetisation, they lack tools to facilitate the governance and quality assessment of their data, resulting not really knowing what data they own or it being non reliable due to its poor quality. External monetisation is usually hindered by the unavailability of trustable mechanisms to perform this exchange or enabling the company to participate in ecosystems like EU data spaces or Gaia-X. DATAMITE is an open-source modular and multi-domain framework that focuses on monetisation through interoperability and data exchange. Its modules offer tools for enhancing data governance, quality and security, but also enabling data sharing to a collection of ecosystems like data spaces, Gaia-X, EOSC or AIoD through a plugin-based approach. It also includes a series of additional support tools to assist on data discovery, ingestion, harmonization or evaluate data fairness, among other.

Keywords: Data Governance · Data Quality · Data Sharing · Data Monetisation.

1 Introduction

In the past decade, data has transformed from a mere resource to a first-class asset for organizations, emerging as one of the most invaluable commodities. It not

only serves as a strategic resource but also presents itself as a potential revenue stream for forward-thinking enterprises, emphasizing the growing significance of data monetisation in today's business landscape.

Data monetisation is often referred as the process of using data to obtain quantifiable economic benefit (e.g., Gartner [15]). There are two types of monetisation: internal and external. Internal includes, mainly, using data to make measurable business performance improvements or inform decisions, aiming at becoming a data-driven organization. External methods include information bartering, selling data outright, or offering information products and services.

Considering that during the last 15 years organizations have been storing an enormous amount of data - some projections suggest that for 2025, the total amount of data stored will exceed 181ZB [38] - thanks to the digitization of the industry and the affordable prices for storage capacity, data monetization emerges as a pivotal opportunity. With the potential to turn this vast reservoir of information into actionable insights, data monetization should be viewed as a silver bullet, unlocking untapped potential and driving sustainable growth for forward-looking companies. But it is not. Reports indicate that up to a 68% of these data is never used [31] or that a staggering 95% of companies suffer from the data-decision-gap [5], i.e., decision makers do not rely on their own data. This not only burdens internal data monetization efforts with an immeasurable opportunity cost but also highlights the critical need for fostering a data-driven culture. External data monetization faces its own challenges, as a lack of data sharing culture and trustworthy exchange mechanisms deterring companies from leveraging this potential revenue stream.

There are several contributing factors to these obstacles in data monetization. First, from the data governance point of view, there is a problem of findability: companies do not frequently adopt data management software offering data catalogues that allows them to find what data is available within the company. Similarly, another barrier is semantic interoperability (even intra-company). Data is usually described technically, but not linked to a company glossary or vocabulary that allows non-technical users to - again - find or understand what data they have. From the data quality front, companies often lack mechanisms to control or monitor data quality, resulting in incomplete, imprecise, inconsistent or invalid data. Any AI model, projection, or analysis based on these data will inevitably throw invalid results, leading to useless, or even worse, detrimental business decisions for the company, leading to the aforementioned data-decision-gap. With respect to data exchange, in addition to European Portals and Data Markets, several initiatives have emerged in recent years, like the International Data Spaces Association [18], Gaia-X [10] or SIMPL [27]. These initiatives propose the creation of federations of companies built on trust, enabling secure exchanges of services and data. In the case of data, these initiatives rely on the use of tools like the Eclipse DataSpace Connector [8], based on the IDS Reference Architecture [36], whose status is still incipient. Despite of the efforts on advancing in terms of data sovereignty, devising tools that grant data owners capabilities to enforce policies regarding data usage or access control, there are

no fully reliable implementations yet. Finally, we can find other reasons like the - until recently - unavailability of open source software tackling several of these issues or the difficulties for SMEs to hire specialised personnel, which is specially relevant given that, in 2023, represented 99.8% of the European non-financial business sector and 64.4% of EU employment [33].

These obstacles are the consequence, as well, of a lack of open source tools providing these kinds of functionalities in an aggregated manner. It is possible to find tools that cover some of these issues individually, like CKAN [4] or Amundsen[23] for data catalogues or Great Expectations [16] regarding quality. There are also new tools aspiring at covering this gap, like OpenMetadata [24] or LinkedIn Datahub [20], which combine features of data governance, quality, discovery and start to implement features related to data products, although do not yet implement functionalities regarding data exchange. This latter issue applies to proprietary solutions, like Collibra [2], Informatica [28], Atlan [19] or Ataccama [9], among others, which are most focused on the in-company management of data, but not yet widely covering data exchange possibilities despite of their costly licenses, often out of reach for SMEs.

We propose DATAMITE, a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework, to improve Data Monetising, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels: internal and external. Internally, users have tools to improve the quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, and are able to upskill on technical and business aspects. Therefore, data becomes trustable, reducing the data-decision gap, and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI. Externally, keeping users in control of their data provides new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders, e.g., in ecosystems like the IDS Data Spaces, data markets or the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In addition, the envisioned architecture enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

DATAMITE main contributions are:

- Providing a framework covering the entire data cycle, from data ingestion to its exchange, e.g., in a Data Space.
- Facilitating interoperability, both within the organization through a data catalogue and glossary, as without, adopting standards like DCAT [40] and DQV [39] or a plugin-based approach to share data in different ecosystems.
- Striving towards data sovereignty by implementing and enforcing access and usage control policies rooted in common, high-level data sharing principles, i.e. a rulebook [37].
- Allowing data sharing in different ecosystems such as IDS Data Spaces, Gaia-X, European portals or Data Markets through a plugin-based approach.

Barriers	Lack of HardWare (HW) Resources	Lack of Data Quality or Governance tools	Lack of tech skills	Lack of data business skills	Lack of data sharing culture	Lack of data Sharing tools
Actors						
SMEs	HW Resources are usually a limitation	Cannot afford costly licenses, insufficient open tools	Limited tech personnel to be trained	Most of the times do not have a clear exploitation strategy	Sharing data is seen as a business risk or as unnecessary in general	Data sharing initiatives are very recent and sharing tools & connectors or data sovereignty tools are still in a very early stage.
LEs	HW Resources are usually abundant, not limiting	Can afford licenses but tools are too rigid or complex	Tech personnel to be upskilled			
Public Admons		Low needs covered with open source tools	Limited tech personnel to be trained	Do not usually have exploitation plans	Opendata platforms, no business risk	Tools need to be standardized and its use generalized
Consequences	Data not stored or analysed. Cost of opportunity	Poor quality data, not trustable, not easy to use by business units. Leads to data decision gaps		Low monetization, deficient business plans		No trading: cost of opportunity Loss of potential collaborations

Fig. 1. Barriers for data monetization and their consequences

The rest of the document is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces several of the barriers and challenges faced by companies. Then, Section 3 presents an analysis of the current state of the art technologies. Sections 4 and 5 provide an overview of the framework and a detailed description of its different modules. DATAMITE validation is presented in Section 6. Finally, a series of open issues are described in Section 7 while the conclusions of this work are presented in 8.

2 Barriers and Challenges

Figure 1 presents a set of relevant barriers to data monetisation, and their consequences. These barriers comprise both technical and non-technical aspects. Beyond the aforementioned lack of open-source data governance, quality and sharing tools, problems like lack of hardware can be addressed by having frameworks like DATAMITE, based on open-source software that can assist Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in becoming enablers for SMEs. Similarly, DATAMITE is creating an open-source community around it that will contribute to alleviate the lack of technical and business skills by providing material in these matters.

Moreover, by implementing a data management framework like DATAMITE, industries can streamline their data processes and reduce the time and resources required to manage data. Furthermore, this software facilitates cross-department and inter-company collaboration, allowing for better exchange of information, enabling identification of new opportunities for innovation and growth, and other key factors, and also increasing this so-called data sharing culture.

However, besides helping with these barriers, there are challenges that the framework must overcome to be appealing for companies. **Compatibility** is one of them. The framework must be easy to integrate with the operations pipeline of an organization to facilitate adoption. For example, industries usually rely on proprietary databases, so DATAMITE must develop data discovery connectors that allow seamless connectivity with several data stores that are widely used by corporations. **Performance** is also key, additional latency would be a deterrent for the adoption of the framework. Meeting the expectations of executives increases considerably the chances of adopting the framework. Another important challenge is **Portability**, being the solution easy to deploy both on-premises, in the cloud or in a hybrid environment, allowing organizations to select preferred

type based on the overall IT strategy, e.g., with resource allocation. This is also specially interesting for large companies with multiple sites. Finally, the issue of **scalability** should also be considered. The framework should be able to scale up and scale down in order to support varying demands for data access and processing in an automated manner. That way it will enable the system to perform in an efficient and stable way independently of the workload. This will also have an impact on the optimization of resources, cost reduction and performance.

3 Related Work

There is a large body of services and applications regarding data governance, quality or security. Specially, during the last years, some proprietary management platforms have improved their functionalities [2, 28] while some others have appeared, both proprietary [9, 19] or open source [24, 20, 23]. Proprietary tend to be costly, hardly affordable for SMEs, but both proprietary and open source have in common that mostly focus on the internal monetisation of data, offering governance and quality functionalities but not including data sharing functionalities. The exception may be OpenMetaData that considers the definition of Data Products, although not integrating connectors to data sharing initiatives.

Regarding data quality, some of these tools can profile data, define their own KPIS (e.g. [9]) or be integrated with quality frameworks like Great Expectations [16] (e.g. [24]). There are specific quality tools, such as Apache Griffin [3] or the aforementioned Great Expectations. The former, open-source solution for distributed data systems, supporting batch and streaming mode with the possibility of defining custom validation rules using a Domain Specific Language in order to meet specific business requirements. The latter, provides an open-source Library of python-oriented methods, called Expectations which is extendable. It allows the integration with a wide range of data sources and orchestrators. However, both are niche services that cannot be compared to DATAMITE.

In general, none of these services consider data sharing, so data quality can be seen as the degree to which data satisfy the requirements defined by the product-owner organization. It misses the importance of data quality representation towards a potential publication of data and its consumption by a data consumer. This can be achieved by using specific protocols like the W3C approach or Amazon's, with DQDL [6]. DATAMITE describes its profiling or quality analysis results using an extended version of DQV [39], to facilitate data interoperability upon its exchange, both for inherent or user-defined metrics.

Regarding Data Sharing, the most relevant initiative would be the creation of European Data Spaces. A data space must provide features like trust for accessing data, privacy and security, sovereignty over the data, interoperability, and mechanisms to add value for sharing data. IDSA is working on the creation of International Data Spaces as systems for sharing data obtaining added value from them, and assuring the requirements that meet the EU commission defined.

GAIA-X is another European initiative proposing the federation of services, basing their approach for data exchange on data spaces and largely coinciding

with the EU Commission requirements. GAIA-X offers an infrastructure to facilitate the consumption of those services, providing transparency, identity and trust services, a federated catalog, data exchange sovereignty, and compliance services, besides enforcing the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Both approaches can be participated through IDSA connectors. These connectors are integral software components facilitating secure and sovereign data sharing among diverse entities, adhering to the IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) [36]. The most relevant implementations would be the Dataspace connector (DSC) [7] and the Eclipse Dataspace connector (EDC) [8]. While EDC is based on DSC, it introduces features such as offering heightened scalability and flexibility, or providing a framework for developing and deploying custom connectors. Furthermore, EDC’s contract negotiation operates asynchronously, and its usage policies are customisable. DSC has been deprecated, while EDC is under active development and is crafted in alignment with IDS standards and the IDS dataspace protocol [17]. This protocol defines schemas and protocols crucial for data exchange within an IDS dataspace, encompassing core functionalities such as data publication, discovery, negotiation, and usage control.

Besides EDC, there are two other major stacks that can be used to build or participate in data spaces or Gaia-X: Gaia-X Federation Services (GXFS) [13] and Gaia-X Web3 Ecosystem (Pontus-X) [25]. GXFS only includes the services necessary to operate a federation, contemplating not only data exchange, but also offerings like cloud services, physical machines, or algorithms. It facilitates data exchange through a distributed file system architecture. Pontus-X facilitates data exchange by promoting standardized protocols and interoperability between research infrastructures. This allows them to talk to each other and share data.

DATAMITE integrates the EDC connector, facilitating the publication of data into Data Spaces or Gaia-X, for which it also integrates several components to ease the participation of an organization into the Gaia-X ecosystem. Similarly, DATAMITE offers an extendable plugin-based to publish data in other ecosystems, such as EOSC [29] or the AIoD [1]. No other data management solution integrates these kind of technologies to the best of our knowledge.

Finally, DATAMITE inherits from previous project like DataPorts [30], an innovative data platform designed to facilitate seamless connectivity among ports. The platform empowers transportation and logistics entities within seaports to consider data as a strategic asset, facilitating data sharing and establishing a foundational basis for the provision of cognitive services.

4 Overview

Figure 2 depicts DATAMITE’s core modules and their components. The framework allows the addition of new datasets, either ingesting them through the *data ingestion and storage* component or the *data discovery tools* that allow the connection to different storage technologies to import the schemas of the required datasets. Both options perform a profiling of the data with the *Quality Evaluator*, based on informative KPIs stored in the *KPI library*. The extracted

Fig. 2. Overview of DATAMITE’s architecture

dataset schema and quality profile metadata follow and extend the DCAT and DQV standards and are sent to the *data governance backend* to be stored in the *metadata repository*. These metadata can be consumed in the *data catalogue* and *data dictionary*, as well as extended through the frontend itself and enriched with terms from vocabularies created and stored in the *data glossary*. Additionally, DATAMITE can track changes in datasets through the *data versioning* and *data lineage* components. Data Quality is not restricted to an initial profile based on informative indicators. Users can define their own qualitative or context-aware KPIs in the *KPI Generator*. These KPIs are stored in the KPI library and made available to be associated to any field in a dataset from the data catalogue. Thus, once a user has associated a series of indicators, informative or context-aware, to a data field she can trigger a quality analysis, which using the Quality Evaluator evaluates the associated indicators offering their result through the catalogue.

Once data has been enriched and its quality assured, users can share them. To do so, they can create a Data Product with the *Data Product Composition* tool, which allows the aggregation of datasets from the catalogue. The data product can be extended with data usage or access control policies, defined with the *Data Sovereignty* components. The data product can be shared to a data space or Gaia-X through the *IDS & GAIA-X connectors* or to other ecosystems via customised plugins in *Other Brokers & plugins*. These plugins map the dataset metadata to the target’s schema, making the publication process smooth and requesting additional information if required. Monitoring data sharing and acting as a local clearing house, the *Logging* component registers any event related to the data products being shared including the usage made by external actors. If these interactions imply payments, the *Payment* support these operations.

Finally, a collection of data support tools can provide punctual additional functionalities. Examples would be the evaluation of the fairness of a dataset,

detecting possible biases; facilitating the harmonization of a dataset according to a predefined schema or vocabulary; or assisting in the pseudoanonymization of a data field before sharing it in a data product.

5 DATAMITE in detail

This section provides an extended description of the goals and functionalities included in the different core modules in DATAMITE.

5.1 Data Governance

The main goal of the Data Governance module offers tools for organizations to ensure their datasets adhere to FAIR principles. The Data Catalogue, Glossary, and Dictionary assist companies in the enrichment of their data, enhancing its findability and accessibility by providing comprehensive metadata, including descriptions and keywords. Interoperability is further facilitated by allowing linking data to terms from custom or imported relevant vocabularies providing business context. Additionally, reusability is fostered by providing also data quality, lineage, or even licensing information, allowing users to understand the scope of the datasets and how to apply them in different contexts. These components are supported by a backend that allows the interaction with a metadata repository, Apache Atlas, and assisted by components devoted to capturing data lineage and providing versioning functionalities for data stored within the framework.

5.2 Data Quality

The Data Quality module goal is the evaluation of the quality of a dataset according to a series of KPIs that can be inherent (e.g., statistics, frequency analysis, histograms, etc) or user defined/context aware. These KPIs are key to not only assess the data value before sharing them but also for a better understanding of their features and the actions needed to improve their quality and increase that value. This module comprises three different components: the Quality Evaluator (QE), the KPI&Rules Generator and the KPI&Rules library.

The QE performs the evaluation of the dataset. It allows two types of flow: a profiling, upon the ingestion of a new dataset or data artifact; or quality analysis, on user demand after she introduces user defined KPIS and links them to fields of a dataset. Both flows follow a configuration file. In the first case, it defines the inherent KPIs to be used in the profiling, including data type dependant (e.g., numeric) and independent (e.g., completeness) KPIs. In the second one, it includes, as well, the user defined KPIs that have been linked to particular dataset fields. Additionally, upon BigData-like datasets, it can be configured to rely on an auxiliary Spark cluster or to perform sampling, alternatively.

The KPI & rules generator allows users to define qualitative indicators that are context aware (e.g., 90% of the samples above X is good). DATAMITE allows the definition of new rules combining existing KPIs from the KPI Library

with new business indicators or aggregating expressions to allow the users for describing their own quality requirements, within the organization context. Both the new user defined KPIs and rules and the predefined inherent indicators are stored in the KPI&Rules library, to be consumed by the QE.

The evaluation results are returned using the DQV model for expressing data quality. DQV has been extended with new classes and relationships to capture DATAMITE’s ability to express new rules as to differentiate between standard and user defined metrics, or to include ‘inherent’ as a new category.

5.3 Data Security

Data Security in DATAMITE consists of two main components devoted to Access Control and to Data Sovereignty. The Access Control component, rooted in Keycloak [35], stands as a cornerstone for secure and efficient user authentication, authorization, and identity management in our framework. Leveraging Keycloak’s robust capabilities, it seamlessly integrates into the architecture, ensuring a streamlined and foolproof access control mechanism. Beyond its fundamental features, Access Control’s support for a multitude of protocols not only extends its versatility but also guarantees compatibility and interoperability within the complex framework of a diverse system. This adaptability makes it an essential component for organizations seeking a robust and comprehensive Access Control solution. Finally, this component interacts with the rest of the modules to ensure fine-grained access control to the data.

To build a strong foundation for data sovereignty, DATAMITE enables automated policy enforcement, namely with two components: the Policy Library and the Policy Engine. The former is a database with an API providing CRUD (Create-Read-Update-Delete) functionalities for both policies and contracts. This enables flexible usage control policy orchestration with ODRL [22], and on the other hand provides a mapping from the concrete policies to the contracts they are derived from. This way, information about which policies to enforce in which cases is retained. The automated enforcement itself is handled by the Policy Engine, providing a way to evaluate ODRL policies.

5.4 Data Sharing

This module primary objective is to facilitate secure and transparent data sharing. DATAMITE uses an extendable plugin-based approach allowing users to publish data into different target ecosystems such as IDSA dataspaces, Gaia-X, European Portals, and Data Markets. By incorporating and expanding upon the IDSA and GAIA-X [10] components, and establishing brokers for European Portals and data markets, the module is designed to deliver a comprehensive range of features. Moreover, new targets can be on-boarded by adding new plugins.

The IDS connectors constitute essential tools for data transfer and are required to participate in IDS data spaces, although they lack universal compatibility. The type of IDS connector utilized depends on those already embraced by a specific IDS data space. These connectors are fortified with robust security

features, including data encryption, secure authentication, and access control methods, to enhance defenses against unauthorized access to sensitive data.

An alternative method involves brokers built upon two distinct technologies: the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) [21] and REST APIs. REST API, designed specifically for networked application architecture, operates as an interface facilitating data exchange and communication among various software systems via HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol). Simultaneously, OAI-PMH [26] orchestrates the metadata extraction process from repositories, fostering consistency between digital archives and repositories by enabling one repository to retrieve and compile metadata from another.

To substantiate these mechanisms for data sharing, DATAMITE incorporates a resilient and auditable logging mechanism to ensure accountability and transparency. This module is meticulously crafted to uphold the fundamental principles of confidentiality, integrity, and availability concerning shared data.

The data product composition serves as an adjunct tool designed to streamline the transformation of raw data into the refined data product that will be shared, either within or without the organisation. It possesses the capability to aggregate data from diverse sources by delineating a new dataset. Furthermore, it facilitates the creation of new datasets through the extraction of subsets based on predefined rules, such as selecting a specific geographic area or time period. The final data product is fashioned through the continued processing supported by data support tools (e.g., applying pseudoanonymisation techniques).

Similarly, if the user wants to publish this data product into a Gaia-X catalog, DATAMITE offers an exporter to convert internal data products into Gaia-X self-descriptions (SD). This component collects the properties used within the internal data product and map these properties to those defined by the Gaia-x Registry service. If any of the mandatory properties within Gaia-X are missing, the user will be asked to introduce them. Once this process is completed, the next step will be to obtain a valid descriptor. To do this, two services defined within Gaia-X will be used: the Gaia-x registration service [14] and the Gaia-x compliance service [12], resulting in a Verifiable Credential that is delivered to the provider. From here on, the provider is free to publish in the Credential Event Service registry [11] so that the catalogs can discover this new credential.

Finally, the payment component is designed to accommodate various charging methods and accounting capabilities, facilitating the monetization of data. This component is intricately linked with the data sovereignty components, given that the charging methods form an integral part of the data usage contract.

5.5 Data Support Tools

DATAMITE offers tools to support different aspects within the data lifecycle. The **Data Ingestion and Storage** component offers an auxiliary S3- based storage repository jointly with bulk and streaming capabilities for data ingestion. Bulk data ingestion is based on S3 multipart, while for the streaming it uses internally Kafka engine with multiple plugins that enable the reception of data

from different technologies or protocols, e.g., Kafka, Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC-UA). Data received is automatically discovered by the Data Catalog.

Data Discovery tools allow connecting to multiple database technologies to discover already existing datasets and import their metadata descriptions into the catalog, performing a quality profiling as well. This component is also plugin-based, allowing the connection to new storage technologies by simply adding a new script for that technology based on a template.

The **Anonymization component** allows for the enhancement of data security, characterized by its generic applicability rather than domain specificity, ensuring comprehensive data anonymization. This tool effectively informs users about sensitive data within the dataset and offers anonymization techniques tailored to the specific content. Subsequently, it furnishes the anonymized dataset, affording users the capability to verify the efficacy of privacy-preserving techniques within the dataset.

The **Data Harmonisation component** facilitates the problem of accessing heterogeneous data from a common domain by enabling the expression of data residing in a particular data source using a common predefined format, model and vocabulary, and hence facilitate intra- or inter-organization utilization. This tool enables suitable users to examine the data storage models in use, map their elements with the corresponding entities of a predefined reference model and/or align them with particular vocabularies through a semi-automatic process. Consequently, data findability, accessibility, interoperability and reuse (FAIR) [41] can be significantly boosted.

The **Fairness and Data Bias Evaluation** aims to assist users on understanding deficiencies in case of fairness on their datasets. Furthermore, datasets with mitigated bias have increased visibility, and the tool will allow users to better understand bias in datasets and navigate the legal and ethical landscape. The tool works by marking attributes in a field as protected or sensitive (e.g., typical attributes would be gender, ethnicity, religion, colour, or age) and evaluating the dataset according to a set of indicative fairness metrics. Depending on the result of this evaluation, it offers suggestions on how to reduce the bias (if any) according to a series of mitigation techniques. The elimination of such biases becomes paramount to prevent the deterioration of discriminatory tendencies

6 Validation

The validation of DATAMITE takes place along 3 different use cases with 2 pilots each. The use cases and pilots are described below.

Data exchange within large corporations: two different cases are contemplated (I) Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange and (II) Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange pilot. In (I) is participated by a multi-domain corporation - Grupo Gimeno, taking advantage of a local DIH - ITI, to "test before invest" the framework. In (II), OTE aims at improving data management across different companies within the corporation, and the joint of exploitation of datasets

in different internal data lakes. Both scenarios share goals like improving data governance, quality and interoperability within the company. Similarly, sharing is relevant, both within and without the company. The latter case will be tested by facilitating data sharing into EOSC.

Data exchange in data spaces: observing (I) Data sharing with Service Providers a Data Space, and (II) Open Data in Data Spaces. (I) is participated by CERTH and HEDNO with the goal of improving data management within the company (enhancing data governance and quality) while experimenting with data spaces as a mechanisms to reliably share data with service providers. In (II) E-Redes aims at improving its Open Data portal and, at the same time, assess the use of Data Spaces and/or Gaia-X to increase the visibility of their open data. Besides the interest on improving governance and quality, there is a focus on the usage of the EDC connector as well as the definition and use of data sovereignty policies.

Data sharing with other initiatives: includes (I) Connecting eDWIN [34] to Data Markets, and (II) Connecting MISTRAL [32] to the EU AIoD Platform. (I) puts the focus on improving the governance, quality and exploitation of agri-food data from the eDWIN platform, operated by the Polish public WODR centre and Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC). Complementary, data sharing will be tested in two ways. First, creating plugins to publish data into a data market to facilitate data trading. Second testing data exchange via data space. In (II), The CINECA consortium and AIoD [1] collaborate to bring data from the MISTRAL portal to the AIOD platform, opening these relevant resources to AI practitioners around Europe.

Besides the specific goals of the different pilots, the different deployments of the framework will allow for testing the framework according to the challenges mentioned in Section 2: compatibility, performance, portability and scalability.

7 Discussion

This paper has described the benefits of DATAMITE and how it will assist organisations in monetising their data. However, there are some limitations to the framework, specially due to the current state of the art. In this section, we elaborate on these limitations and how we alleviate their effects.

First, we acknowledge that the maturity of certain data sharing technologies and initiatives is still questionable. This applies to EDC connectors as well as to Data Spaces, Gaia-X or the AIoD. For this reason, DATAMITE does not limit to these initiatives. It adopts a plugin-based approach that allows for the implementation of new connectors to any other data sharing ecosystem, as it is the case with marketplaces, or other EU portals for data exchange.

Second, Data Sovereignty and the enforcement of data usage or data access control policies is still incipient, not being enough, in most cases, for production environments. DATAMITE provides the tools to create policies, but the enforcement depends on the targeted ecosystems. When the technology is more mature DATAMITE should still be valid to define and apply these policies.

Finally, several standards are currently evolving, like those related to data spaces or those related, for instance, to the representation of data or its quality. DATAMITE is based on open-source and flexible tools that should allow to adapt to these changes in the future.

8 Conclusions

Framework offers an open-source modular and multi-domain framework that aims at boosting how organisations monetise their data. As has been shown, it is performed at two different levels, internal and external. Internally, specially assisting from the point of view of data governance, improving how data can be found, accessed, reused or facilitating interoperability, helping organisations to adhere to the FAIR principles. Additionally, this can be seen as an enabler for sharing good data in ecosystems like those offered by Gaia-X, EU Data Spaces or other platforms like the AIOd or marketplaces. Moreover, to this respect, data can be shared offering quality information that has been included applying standards like DQV.

DATAMITE is conceived as an open-source and modular to facilitate its adoption by organisations, trying that aspects like compatibility or portability, among others, are not a deterrent for its adoption. Similarly, in several of its components (e.g., data sharing or data discovery) follows plugin based approaches, thinking of its potential extensions according to user needs. Altogether, DATAMITE not only should be able to overcome several of the barriers described in Section 2, but also the challenges enumerated.

References

1. Ai-on-demand platform. <https://www.ai4europe.eu/>
2. Ai starts with trusted data. <https://www.collibra.com/>
3. Big data quality solution for batch and streaming. <https://griffin.apache.org/>
4. Ckan: The world's leading open source data management system. <https://ckan.org/>
5. Data in context: Closing the data decision gap, <https://www.quantexa.com/resources/closing-the-data-decision-gap/>
6. Data quality definition language (dqdl) reference. <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/glue/latest/dg/dqdl.html>
7. Dataspace connector dsc. <https://international-data-spaces-association.github.io/DataspaceConnector>
8. Eclipse edc connector. <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>
9. The future of ai is built on quality data. <https://www.ataccama.com/>
10. Gaia-x. <https://gaia-x.eu/gaia-x-framework>
11. Gaia-x ces. <https://gaia-x.eu/news-press/gaia-x-and-catalogues>
12. Gaia-x compliance. <https://compliance.gaia-x.eu>
13. Gaia-x federation services. <https://www.gxfs.eu/>
14. Gaia-x registry. <https://registry.gaia-x.eu>
15. Gartner glossary: Data monetisation. <https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/data-monetization>

16. Have confidence in your data, no matter what. <https://greatexpectations.io/>
17. Ids protocol. <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/dataspace-protocol/overview/readme>
18. International data spaces: The future of the data economy is here. <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>
19. The leading third-gen data catalog. <https://atlan.com/>
20. LinkedIn datahub. <https://datahubproject.io/>
21. Oai-pmh. <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh>
22. ODRL information model 2.2. <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>
23. Open source data discovery and metadata engine. <https://www.amundsen.io/>
24. Openmetadata. a single place to discover, collaborate and get your data right. <http://open-metadata.org>
25. Pontus-x: Streamlined interoperability across digital service ecosystems. <https://portal.minimal-gaia-x.eu/>
26. Restapi. <https://docs.github.com/en/rest?apiVersion=2022-11-28>
27. Simpl: Cloud-to-edge federations empowering eu data spaces. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>
28. Turn data chaos into data clarity with ai. <https://www.informatica.com/platform.html>
29. Your unified access to the european hub of research data, tools and services for innovation and education. <https://eosc-portal.eu/>
30. Dataports. <https://dataports-project.eu> (2019)
31. Rethink data put more of your business data to work, from edge to cloud. https://www.seagate.com/files/www-content/our-story/rethink-data/files/Rethink_Data_Report_2020.pdf (Jul 2020)
32. CINECA: Mistral portal. <https://www.hpc.cineca.it/projects/mistral/>
33. Di Bella, L., Katsinis, A., Laguera Gonzalez, J., Odenthal, L., Hell, M., Lozar, B.: Annual report on european smes 2022/2023. Scientific analysis or review KJ-NA-31-618-EN-N (online), Luxembourg (Luxembourg) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.2760/028705> (online)
34. eDWIN: edwin platform. <https://www.edwin.gov.pl/>
35. Hat, R.: Keycloak:open source identity and access management, <https://www.keycloak.org/>
36. Otto, B., Steinbuss, S., Teuscher, A., Lohmann, S.e.a.: IDS Reference Architecture Model (Version 3.0). Tech. rep., International Data Spaces Association (2019). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105529>, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105529>
37. Pitkänen, O., Luoma-Kyyny, J.: Rulebook for a fair data economy. Tech. rep., Sitra (2019), <https://www.sitra.fi/en/publications/rulebook-for-a-fair-data-economy/>
38. Taylor, P.: Data growth worldwide 2010-2025 (Nov 2023), <https://www.statista.com/statistics/871513/worldwide-data-created/>
39. W3C: Data on the web best practices: Data quality vocabulary. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/> (2016)
40. W3C: Data catalog vocabulary (dcat) - version 2. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/> (2020)
41. Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., et al.: The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data* **3**(1), 1–9 (2016)